

ANALYSIS OF BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS IN *H. PURPURASCENS* INFLORESCENCE USING HPLC AND FTIR TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

Plants play a crucial role in ensuring the survival of humanity by offering food, medicine, clothing, etc. This is the era of harnessing the secondary metabolites from plants for their medicinal properties. The bioactive constituent present in plants are utilized either directly or isolated to synthesize novel drugs. Hence an attempt has been made to identify the bioactive components from the inflorescence of *Hedyotis purpurascens* using HPLC and FTIR. HPLC profiling of *H. purpurascens* inflorescence reported the presence of nine major metabolites. The FTIR analysis evidenced the occurrence of phenols, alkanes, alcohols and amines. The current investigation contributes to our knowledge about the phytochemical diversity of *H. purpurascens* inflorescence as a potential candidate in treating various diseases.

KEYWORDS: HPLC, FTIR, *Hedyotis purpurascens*, Rutin, Secondary metabolites

INTRODUCTION

Plants have formed the basis of sophisticated traditional medicine systems that have been in existence for thousands of years and continue to provide mankind with new remedies^[1]. Medicinal plants have been used for centuries in various cultures around the world for their therapeutic properties. Phytochemicals are found in plants and depending on their role in plant metabolism they are classified as primary or secondary constituents. Chemical principles from natural sources have become much simpler and have contributed significantly to the development of new drugs from medicinal plants^[2]. The valuable medicinal properties of different plants are due to presence of several constituents i.e. saponins, tannins, alkaloids, alkenyl phenols, glycol- alkaloids, flavonoids, sesquiterpenes lactones, terpenoids and phorbol esters^[3]. Within a decade, there were a number of dramatic advances in analytical techniques including HPLC, UV, FTIR, NMR and GC-MS that were powerful tools for separation, identification and structure determination of phytochemicals^[4]. An attempt has been made in the present study is to determine the bioactive compounds present in the *H. purpurascens* inflorescence ethanolic extract with the aid of HPLC and FTIR Techniques, which may provide an insight in its use of tradition medicine.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of crude plant extract:

Fresh and healthy inflorescence of *Hedyotis purpurascens* were harvested, shade dried and coarsely powdered for extraction. 50g of coarsely powdered plant samples were exhaustively extracted with hexane, diethyl ether and ethanol using soxhlet apparatus. The ethanolic extract of this inflorescence was taken for further studies.

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopic Investigation:

The extracts were examined under visible and UV light for proximate analysis. FTIR spectrophotometer analysis, the extracts were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 mins and filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper by using a high-pressure vacuum pump. The sample is diluted to 1:10 with the same solvent. The extracts were scanned in the wavelength ranging from 260-900 nm using Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometer and the characteristic peaks were detected. FTIR analysis was performed using Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometer system, which was used to detect the characteristic peaks in ranging from 400-4000 cm⁻¹ and their functional groups. The peak values of FTIR were recorded. Each and every analysis was repeated twice for the spectrum confirmation.

High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) Analysis:

Sample preparation: The sample was prepared according to the procedure. The extraction was carried out using 2 ml offermented broth with 50 mL of 95% ethanol under 80 kHz, 45°C in ultrasonic extraction device for 30 min, repeated twice. The extract was collected and filtered; the filtrate was dried at 50° C under reduced pressure in a rotary evaporator. The dried crude extract was dissolved in the 100 ml mobile phases. After filtering through a filter paper and a 0.45 µm membrane filter (Millipore), the extract was injected into HPLC.

HPLC conditions: Flavonoids were analyzed using an RP-HPLC method^[5] Shimadzu Corp., Kyoto, consisting of a LC10 ATV p pump, SCL 10 A system controller and a variable Shimadzu SPD- 10 ATV p UV VIS detector and a loop injector with a loop size of 20µl. The peak area was calculated by a CLASS VP software. Reverse phase chromatographic analysis was carried out in isocratic conditions using a C18 reverse phase column (250×4.6 mmi. d., particle size 5µm, Luna 5µC-18; phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA) at 25°C. The gradient elution of solvent A [water-acetic acid (25:1 v/v)] and solvent B (methanol) had a

significant effect on the resolution of compounds. As a result, solvent gradients were formed using dual pumping system by varying the proportion of solvent A to solvent B. Solvent B was increased to 50% in 4 min and subsequently increased to 80% in 10 min at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. Detection wavelength was 280 nm.

RESULTS

The present study has been carried out to find out the bioactive compounds present in the inflorescence of *H.purpurascens*. The pharmacological aspect of any plant is due to the presence of the secondary metabolites. Alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, tannins, terpenoids and steroids are some of the active compounds that are found in plants and are widely used to treat various diseases.

Functional groups identification

The FTIR spectrum was used to identify functional groups of the active components present in plant samples, based on the peaks values in the region of IR radiation. The results of FTIR analysis have confirmed the presence of alcohol, phenol, alkanes, amines and nitro group of compounds. (Fig-1 and Table-1)

Fig 1: FTIR spectrum of ethanol

Table-1 Functional groups in *H.purpurascens* inflorescence

S.NO	FUNCTIONAL GROUP/ASSINGMENT	INTENSITY	CHARACTERISTIC ABSORPTION (cm-1)
1	Phenols & Alcohols		3362.24
	O-H (free), usually sharp O-H (H-Bonded), usually broad	Stretching Vibration, Strong	
2	Amines		3144.95
	N-H	Stretching Vibration, strong	
3	Alkanes		2921.94
	CH ₃ , CH ₂ & CH 2 or 3 bands	Stretching Vibration, Strong	
4	Alcohols & phenols		1395.21
	O-H bending (in plane)	Bending Vibration, Medium	
5	Amines		1057.85
	C-N	Stretching Vibration, medium	
6	Arenes or Amines		852
	C-H bending & ring puckering NH ₂ & N-H wagging (shifts on H-bonding)	Bending Vibration, strong-Medium Bending Vibration, variation	

Determination of compounds in HPLC analysis

The bioactive compounds in the ethanolic extract of *H.purpurascens* were identified using HPLC technique. The sample was made to run against the standards rutin and quercetin at 280nm. From the chromatogram, it is noticeable that the standard rutin has the retention time of 3.811, quercetin of 6.823 and the extract at 3.795. Coming out of the results, it can be interpreted that the retention time of Rutin and the sample remains compatible with each other (3.811 & 3.795). Hence it is elucidated that rutin, a flavonoid is present in the inflorescence of the plant *Heyotis purpurascens*. Rutin is a natural flavonoid compound and has an extensive range of therapeutic potentials [6]. Rutin has been widely used in treating disease, its several pharmacological activities including antiallergic [7], anti-inflammatory and vasoactive, antitumour, antibacterial, antiviral and antiprotozoal properties [8]. From the above findings it is substantiated that the inflorescence of the plant *H.purpurascens* can be used to treat various diseases. Hence this plant extract remains viable in the context of pharmacology and pharmaceuticals. (Fig -2-4 and Table 2,3)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

Fig: 2 HPLC Chromatogram of sample at 280 nm

Table: 2 Peak Table of sample

S.No	Retention time (min)	Area (mAU)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Conc.
1	3.795	1104770	131.919	1.1	27.287
2	4.27	29856	5.372	0.03	0.737
3	4.891	2436380	156.925	2.45	60.178
4	5.766	276022	12.622	0.276	6.818
5	12.176	32292	2.211	0.03	0.798
6	13.608	39555	2.857	0.04	0.977
7	14.654	36813	2.046	0.036	0.909
8	23.078	37328	3.128	0.037	0.922
9	30.189	55620	31	0.055	1.374

Fig: 3 HPLC Chromatogram of standards at 280 nm

Table: 3 Peak Table of Standard compared to sample

S.No	Standards/ Sample extract	Retention time (min)	Area [mAU]	Height [mAU]	Area (%)	Conc. (in µg/ml)	
1	Rutin	3.811	694.159	38.125	100	10	
2	Quercetin	6.823	1845.12	60.025	100	10	
3	Ethanollic inflorescence extract	Rutin	3.795	11047.70	131.91	27.29	Present
		Quercetin	----	----	----	----	Absent

Fig: 4 Chemical Structure of Rutin

CONCLUSION

The present study has been carried out in the ethanolic inflorescence extract of *H.purpurascens*. The study revealed the presence of bioactive compounds and functional groups that are responsible for several biological activities that helps in curing diseases. So it is concluded that this plant part could serve as a potential agent for the production of novel drugs.

REFERENCE

- 1) Gurib-Fakim, A. (2006). Medicinal plants: traditions of yesterday and drugs of tomorrow. *Molecular aspects of Medicine*, 27(1):1-93.
- 2) Cox, P.A. (1990). Ethnopharmacology and the search for new drugs Bioactive Compounds from Plants Ciba Foundation Symposium, Chichester. *John Wiley & Sons*, 154:40.
- 3) Cox, P & Balick, M. (1994). The ethnobotanical approach to drug discovery. *Sci American*, 82.
- 4) Roberts, J.K.M., & Xia, J.H. (1995). High-resolution NMR methods for study of higher plants. *Methods Cell Biol*, 49:245–258.
- 5) Weerasak Samee, & Suwanna Vorarat. (2007) Simultaneous Determination of Gallic acid, Catechin, Rutin, Ellagic Acid and Quercetin in Flower Extracts of *Michelia alba*, *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Nelumbo nucifera* by HPLC. *Thai Pharm Health Sci J*, 2:131-137.

- 6) Negahdari, R., Bohlouli, S., Sharifi, S., Maleki Dizaj, S., Rahbar Saadat, Y., Khezri, K., Jafari, S., Ahmadian, E., Gorbani Ja handizi, N., & Raeesi, S. (2021). Therapeutic benefits of rutin and its nanoformulations. *Phytotherapy Research*, 35(4):1719–1738.
- 7) Zwirtes de Oliveira, I. R., Fernandes, S. C., & Vieira, I. C. (2006). Development of a biosensor based on gilo peroxidase immobilized on chitosan chemically crosslinked with epichlorohydrin for determination of rutin. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical analysis*, 41(2), 366–372.
- 8) Calabrò, M. L., Tommasini, S., Donato, P., Stancanelli, R., Raneri, D., Catania, S., Costa, C., Villari, V., Ficarra, P., & Ficarra, R. (2005). The rutin/ β -cyclodextrin interactions in fully aqueous solution: Spectroscopic studies and biological assays. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, 36(5):1019–1027.